

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Effect of Scaffolding Teaching Method on Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics

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Abstract

The current research focuses on the scaffolding instructional technique in improving students' understanding level in the subject of mathematics. The study was experimental in nature and thereby experiment was conducted at Government School Daraban Kalan, District Dera Ismail Khan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Two groups are formed of 10th grade students on the basis on pre-test score. Twenty-five (25) students were randomly assigned to control group whereas 25 students assigned randomly to experimental group. Control group were taught to conventional style of teaching while treatment group was taught by using scaffolding instructional approach. Pretest and Posttest was developed from 10th grade mathematics syllabus. The result of the study reveals that students secured high marks in experimental group as compared to control group. The study concluded that scaffolding instructional strategy enhances the students learning in academic achievement.

Keywords: Scaffolding; Academic achievement

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1. Introduction

Education plays a crucial role in social life of an individual and essential part for personality grooming. In fact, education is a source of self-recognition and develops the one's attitude in proper direction. Generally, education plays a vital role in the social and economic development of the country. Without education, no country can make development in any field. More specifically, education is a main source of knowledge for the society because social values can be transmitted to generation through education (Ozturk, 2008).

Education plays an important role in individual personally and one's personality can be changes through learning. Moreover, individual's character, attitude and behavior can be modified through learning. But individual learning can be improved through appropriate method of teaching. (Harun &

Salamuddin, 2010). Practitioner emphasis on student-centered teaching approach because it helps learners to develop meaning if they themselves experience it. In addition, it is important for students to associate their prior knowledge to new concepts and idea shared in the class. Conclusively, learning becomes real and tangible among students in the class (Dano-Hinosolango, & Vedula-Dinagsao, 2014).

Scaffolding instructional strategy refers as a student-centered teaching approach that is used to accomplish maximum objectives in learning process. The key aim of scaffolding strategy is to accomplish desirable objective in a stipulated time period and engage students actively in teaching learning process (Alake & Ogunseemi, 2013). Scaffolding was closely link with the socio-cultural theory of Lev Semenovich Vygotsky, and specifically with his concept of Zone Proximal Development (ZPD). The key theme of the ZPD is the